

A Possibility in Connected History: Nicholas Roerich

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This write-up is based on a visit to Bharat Kala Bhawan, BHU and the State Museum at Allahabad. The Kala Bhawan houses a gallery display of paintings by Russian painter, Nicholas Roerich and a few by his son S Roerich. These paintings are rich in colours and details. The paintings by Nicholas bear the majesty of the many mountains that are so richly depicted in his works on display there. Almost all the paintings had mountains, open sky, in various hues of red & blue. The human or anthropomorphic subjects present all have features and clothing similar to that one sees in Ladakh or Gangtok, the temples or palaces displayed also seemed like those in Tibetan or a Buddhist-mountain-esqe style. There is also a sketch-portrait of Nicholas Roerich by his son on display, looking like an old, mountain-man. The paintings of S. Roerich seemed similar to those of his father.

I didn't know anything about Roerich before my visit to Kala Bhawan, and even after that, not much beyond what little was written on the info-plaque on the wall there at the gallery. It was not hard to forget about him, for there are far more grand and appealing paintings (that of Alice Boner and others in Banaras gallery) & artefacts as the old map of Banaras, Aurangzeb's *farmaan* about Gyanvapi-Kashivishwanath, Ramnagar Ramleela's masks, even if we don't count the displays of the galleries one explores prior to the Roerich gallery. Not until my visit to the Allahabad Museum a few months later, that Roerich became the 'subject' of my curiosity. The Roerich gallery at the Allahabad Museum is far bigger and had many more paintings than the one there at Kala Bhawan. The paintings there too have the similar style as those at the Kala Bhawan, and many of the paintings had an element of 'supernatural' or 'fantasy' about them,

not simply a depiction of stone Buddhas or monasteries on the mountain slopes- but of something more, beyond the scenic beauty. Thus, only after this second encounter with Roerich, I tried to know something more about him.

‘Paintings (including drawing, sketches, diagrams and the like) ...by... N. Roerich’¹ were declared national art treasures by the Government of India in ‘regard of their artistic and aesthetic value’ in 1979. This made him, the only non-Indian, a part of the ‘*Navratnas*’, the nine ‘national treasure’ artists of India, whose works enjoy special protection under the Antiquities and Art Treasure Act, 1972.²

Born to a famous notary Konstantin F. Roerich and his wife Maria in Saint-Petersburg on October 9, 1874, was a boy with versatile gifts. Nicholas ‘Nikolai Konstantinovich’ Roerich can be compared to the ‘titans’ of the Renaissance, for his varied and rich legacy- more than seven thousand paintings, and numerous literary works as books, essays, and diaries. No one country or organisation can claim to own all of Roerich.³

In 1901, Roerich married the woman who would be one of the most profound influence and inspiration for all his works. Helena Shaposhnikova was a true companion to Roerich on all planes, something which their son Svetoslav Roerich explains as ‘[s]upplementing each other, they seemed to merge in a richest harmony of intellectual and spiritual expression.’⁴

Despite being interested in arts, Roerich’s father insisted on him studying law. Thus, Nicholas Roerich got trained both as a lawyer and an artist. During college, Roerich met some of the leading artists and composers of Russia of that time, and through them, his future wife, Helena.⁵

Helena herself had deep interests in arts, history and philosophy, which will be one of the reasons for the results that Roerich’s companionship to each other produced, not only in the sphere of art and literature but also in spiritualism, philosophy, and even international diplomacy.⁶

Over the course of their lives, the Roerichs will travel the world, meeting the leading figures of the day, engaging in deep philosophical discussion, and experiencing firsthand the universality and unity of life and human history that they had very early come to believe. In the summers of 1903-04, they toured about 40 cities in Russia, exploring the ruins, ancient churches, castles, city walls- and the idea, for what later materialised as the Roerich Pact, was born.⁷

May 29, 1913 saw the opening of one of the most famous collaborative works of the Nicholas Roerich and other leading figures of theatre of the time- Igor Stravinsky's ballet 'The Rite of Spring'.⁸ In the pre-World War I period, Nicholas Roerich came under the influence of Theosophists, probably due to his wife's interests. They were experimental in their spiritual searches and had deep interest in eastern religious and spiritual practises. Roerich's art of the period, some of which included commissions for the Church and had Christian themes, show a marked influence of this 'eastern quest'. When the couple moved to London in 1919, they joined the Theosophical Society.⁹ This also marked the beginning of their life-long love for India.

However, before coming to India in 1923, the Roerich family first stayed in London, and then the USA. While in London, they met leading artists and writers of the time, one of them being Rabindranath Tagore, with whom Nicholas Roerich developed a close friendship and correspondence between them lasted all their life.¹⁰

On May 8, 1923 Roerichs stepped on the Indian shores, undertaking a voyage through the Indian Ocean. When they wanted to meet Rabindranath Tagore, they were made to explore the city, since they had assumed there was only one 'poet Tagore' in Calcutta. They didn't meet Tagore, the Nobel Laureate but met his brother, Abanindranath Tagore, and a Bose-Sen, 'pupil of the closest pupil of Vivekanand', and also Sister Christine, 'almost the only living pupil of

Vivekanand'. When visiting a bank in Bombay, Roerich was amused to find a cow exiting the bank. He, as one usually is, was mesmerized by Benares, for him the city encased a unity in diversity, especially in architecture. His diaries offer a much-nuanced narrative of the places, people, their day-to-day life, than many of the contemporary travellers.¹¹

From 1925-28, with a short visit to Russia in 1926, Roerich spent their time exploring Himalayas, ultimately settling in the Kulu Valley (India) in 1935. However, he was neither ignorant nor novice of geo-politics and international relations. The distrust of the British-Indian authorities, so much that they even asked the British settlers of Kullu Valley to inform them of Roerich's activities, and Roerich's own visit to Russia carrying the 'Letters of Mahatama', are some of the instances which shows both his own ambitions and the importance others accorded him, for a more active role in international affairs.¹²

The other significant act of international cooperation was the movement for 'Roerich Pact' which came into effect in 1935 after the US and 20 other nations of Pan-American Union signed it. This 'Treaty on the Protection of Artistic and Scientific Institutions and Historic Monuments', which only is known as 'Roerich Pact', was a significant international attempt to preserve the heritage monuments, especially during armed conflicts. Similar to the 'Red Cross', but for heritage sites. Its impact is significant for, despite being limited to Americas, the movement of 'Pax Cultura' had a global support network, one being the Nagari Pracharini Sabha (Varanasi), probably the oldest literary society in India. The Banner of Peace, designed by Roerich himself, laid the foundation for the 'Blue Shield', and the pact paved way for the Hague Convention of 1954 and its subsequent protocols.¹³ And for all this and much more, Roerich was nominated 3 times for the Noble Peace Prize, first being in 1929, and subsequently in 1932 and in 1935 (when he had double nominations).¹⁴

Roerich and his family had made India their home, but are little known in present day. The Act of 1972, declaring his and other artists' works as protected, some believe, is one of the reasons for this ignorance and forgetfulness towards him- he was confined to the galleries and museums.¹⁵ The interest towards Roerich from historical point of view is also wanting, for he undertook extensive explorations of not just the mountains, where his heart dwelled, but also of the wider world. His interests being many, his perspective on the contemporary colonial India and the global system may offer us unique insight for historical research.

Pictures/illustrations from Klimentieva, 'Nicholas Roerich':

1. Banner of Peace

2. Nicholas Roerich. Path to Shambhala, 1933. Tempera on canvas, 46.5 x 78.5 cm. Nicholas Roerich Museum, New York.

3. Nicholas Roerich. Song of the Morning. Decorative Panel from "Dreams of Wisdom" series, 1920. Tempera on canvas, 235 x 122 cm. Nicholas Roerich Museum, New York.

Note:

1. The Gazette of India notification- The Antiquities & Art Treasures Rules, 1973: accessed via official website of Archaeological Survey of India- <https://asi.nic.in/wpcontent/uploads/2015/07/12.pdf> (pg 26)

2. *ibid*

3. See entry on Nicholas Roerich (under Roerich's family), on the website of the International Centre of the Roerichs: <https://www.en.icr.su/family/nkr/index/php>

4. *ibid*- as quoted from 'S. Roerich. Striving for the Beautiful. M.:ICR, 1993. P.49'

5. See sections 'Childhood', and 'Birth of the Family' in Nicholas P Banykin, The Roerich Family, (nd): Webpage accessed on 20/08/2020- <https://emrism.agniage.net/english/semrer/semrer.htm>

6. *Ibid*- section 'Adolescence'

7. See 'Biography' section on website of the Nicholas Roerich Museum, New York-
<http://www.roerich.org/roerich-biography.php>
8. *ibid*
9. See Louise Hardiman, 'The Loving Labourer through Space and Time: Aleksandra Pogosskasia, Theosophy, and Russian Arts and Crafts, c. 1900-1917' in L. Hardiman and N. Kozicharow eds, *Modernism and the Spiritual in Russian Art: New Perspectives*. Cambridge, UK: Open Book Publishers, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0115>; see also Note 26 of same.
10. Section 'The Beginning of the Path' in Banykin, *The Roerich Family*
11. See Chapter 1 'India (1924)' in Nicholas Roerich, *Altai-Himalaya: A Travel Diary*, New York: Nicholas Roerich Museum, 2017, as webpage accessed on 20/08/2020-
<http://www.roerich.org/roerich-writings-altai-himalaya.php>
12. See Victoria Klimentieva, 'Nicholas Roerich: In Search of Shambhala', MA Thesis, University of Texas at Austin, 2009 (pg 61-69): accessed on 20/08/2020-
<http://repositories.lib.utexas.edu/bitstream/handle/2152/ETD-UT-2009-08358/KLIMENTIEVA-THESIS.pdf> ; also see John Zubrzycki, 'The Roerich Story', *LiveHistoryIndia*, April 18, 2018: <https://www.peepultree.world/livehistoryindia/story/places/the-roerich-storyn> accessed on 30/08/2024
13. See section 'Roerich Pact' on website of International Roerich Memorial Trust, Kullu Valley- <http://irmtkullu.com/the-roerich-pact/> ; also see K. Warikoo, 'Editor's Note', *Journal of Himalayan Research and Cultural Foundation*, Vol. 15 No. 4 July-December 2011 (pg 2)
14. See section 'Nomination Archive' on The Nobel Prize website: accessed on 20/08/2020-
https://www.nobelprize.org/nomination/archive/show_people.php?id=7805
15. See Anvisha Manral 'The Antiquities and Art Treasure Act ails India's tangible heritage; is the 2017 draft bill constructive?', *Firstpost.com*, Sept 07, 2019: accessed on 20/08/2020-
<https://www.firstpost.com/living/antiquities-and-art-treasures-act-1972-ails-indias-cultural-property-is-the-2017-draft-bill-constructive-7233531.html/amp>